

CHARACTERIZATION AND THERMAL EFFECT ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF BIOMATERIAL-REINFORCED-POLYPROPYLENE

A. D. Ngo¹, T. Dhaouadi¹, J. B. Ragu¹, A. Rodriguez-Uribe², M. Misra², A. K. Mohanty²

¹ Laboratoire de fabrication et de caractérisation de matériaux composites, Département de génie mécanique, École de technologie supérieure (U. du Québec), 1100 Notre-Dame West, Montréal, Québec, H3C1K3, Canada

² Bioproducts Discovery and Development Centre, Department of Plant Agriculture, Crop Science Building, University of Guelph, Guelph, N1G2W1, ON, Canada, Country

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ABSTRACT

This study consists in characterizing the mechanical properties in tensile, bending and impact resistance of three biocomposite materials. The studied materials are composed of the same matrix (polypropylene (PP)/polyolefin elastomer (POE)) reinforced by three different reinforcements. Formulations (F1), (F2) and (F3) are respectively reinforced with biocarbon particles, miscanthus fibres and the third reinforcement is a mixture of biocarbon particles and miscanthus fibres. To improve the adhesion between the reinforcements and the matrix, modified polypropylene anhydride (MAPP) was added to the biocomposites. The results suggests that in general the biomaterials reinforcements increase the tensile and flexural properties of PP/POE matrix, except in the case of biocarbon particles for the tensile strength. On the contrary, they reduce the impact resistance of the matrix. The temperature has detrimental effect on the tensile and flexural properties of the biocomposites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Manufacturers in the automotive sector have an interest in finding lighter materials in order to reduce the use of energy and to respect the regulations imposed in order to reduce the emission of greenhouse gases. Talc/Polypropylene composite, a lightweight material is widely used in the automotive sector because of the good compromise between rigidity and impact resistance. A novel class of biomaterials reinforced thermoplastic was engineered by the Bioproducts Discovery and Development Centre of University of Guelph, from pyrolysed miscanthus based carbon particle [1], miscanthus fibre, poly (octane ethylene) elastomer (POE) and polypropylene (PP), as alternative material due to their lower weight, cost and less harmful to manufacturing tools. This study aimed at characterizing the mechanical properties of these new materials as well as the thermal effect on their tensile and flexural properties.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The PP matrix of the composites contained 5wt% of POE elastomer. As reinforcement materials, 30wt% of biocarbon particles of 0.4mm in size and 30wt% of miscanthus fibres of 4mm in length were incorporated respectively into the first (F1) and second (F2) biocomposites. The third biocomposite (F3) contained 15wt% of biocarbon particles and 15wt% of miscanthus fibres. 3wt% of maleic anhydride grafted PP (MAPP) was added to the biocomposites to help controlling the adhesion between the reinforcement material and the matrix. The biocomposites were melt-blended and then injection-molded to tensile, flexural and impact coupons for testing.

The tensile and flexural tests were performed according to the ASTM D638 and D790 whereas the standard ASTM D4381 was used for the un-notched Izod impact testing. As for the thermal effect, the tensile and flexural tests were conducted at 25°C, 35°C, 46°C, 54°C and 66°C. At least five specimens were tested for each condition.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Tensile properties

Table 1 shows the tensile modulus and tensile strength of three tested biocomposites F1, F2 and F3, whereas figure 1 presents their tensile properties compared to that of the matrix (PP/POE) and the Talc/PP commercial composite (RTP132UV) [2]. It was found that on one hand, the modulus of the matrix was increased by 34%, 107% and 70% for the F1 (PP/POE/Biocarbon 30%wt), F2 (PP/POE/Miscanthus 30%wt) and F3 (PP/POE/Biocarbon 15%wt/ Miscanthus 15%wt) biocomposites respectively. On the other hand, only for the F2 biocomposite, miscanthus fibres increased by 10.5 the tensile strength of the matrix while for the F3 the hybrid reinforcement of miscanthus fibres and biocarbon particles increased it slightly and in the case of F1, biocarbon particles even reduced slightly this property. Compared to that the commercial Talc/PP composite all three biocomposites had better tensile strength but only the F2 had better tensile modulus

Specimen Number	F1		F2		F3	
	Modulus (MPa)	Strength (MPa)	Modulus (MPa)	Strength (MPa)	Modulus (MPa)	Strength (MPa)
1	2485,5	31,57	3890	37,81	3259,6	33,98
2	2420,6	31,18	3898,5	37,03	3137	34,45
3	2596	30,93	3809,3	36,95	3144,9	34,05
4	2405,7	31,13	3845,7	37,48	3100,8	33,47
5	2641,8	30,4	3917,4	37,34	3232,8	34,12
Mean	2509,92	31,04	3872,18	37,32	3175,02	34,01
Standard Deviation	105,16	0,43	43,9	0,35	67,74	0,35

Table 1: Tensile properties of three biocomposites at 25°C.

Figure 2: Tensile properties of three biocomposites compared to that of the matrix and the PP/Talc commercial composite.

Figure 2 shows the fracture surfaces of F1 and F2 biocomposites. It can be observed that the adhesion between the biocarbon particles (a) and the miscanthus fibres (b) with the matrix was not efficient despite the presence of MAPP [2].

Figure 3: Fracture Surface of Biocomposites F1 and F2

Figure 4 presents the harmful thermal effect on the tensile properties of three biocomposites [3].

Figure 4: Tensile properties of three biocomposites at various temperatures (a) Modulus, (b) Strength.

3.2 Flexural properties

Table 2 shows the flexural modulus and the flexural strength of three tested biocomposites F1, F2, F3 and the matrix (PP/POE/MAPP) whereas figure 5 presents their flexural properties compared to that of the matrix and the Talc/PP commercial composite (RTP132UV). The flexural modulus of three biocomposites F1, F2 and F3 was increased 30%, 92% and 60% respectively compared to that of the matrix, whereas the increases in the flexural strength were 5%, 30% and 11% respectively.

Figure 6 shows the reduction of the flexural properties of the studied biocomposites with the increase of temperature [3].

	<i>PP+POE+MAPP</i>		<i>F1</i>		<i>F2</i>		<i>F3</i>	
Sample Number	<i>Modulus (MPa)</i>	<i>Strength (MPa)</i>						
1	1581,4	47,98	2100	51,53	3235,8	59,34	2722,6	55,52
2	1669,8	50,37	2181,1	52,32	3035,3	57,04	2724,2	54,42
3	1655,4	50,12	2100	51,31	3204,6	58,51	2685,6	55,26
4	1649,5	49,28	2219	53,07	3088,3	58,81	2831,9	54,69
5	1633,3	49,08	2130,6	51,42	3177	58,61	2613,3	55,31
Mean	1637,88	49,37	2146,14	51,93	3148,2	58,46	2716,66	55,04
Standard-Deviation	34,18	0,94	52,51	0,75	83,69	0,91	77,26	0,46

Table 2: Flexural properties of three biocomposites at 25°C and matrix material.

Figure 5: Flexural properties of three biocomposites at 25°C, matrix material and commercial reference composite.

Figure 6: Thermal effect on the flexural properties of the studied biocomposites (a) modulus, (b) strength

3 Impact Strength

Table 3 and figure 7 show results of the unnotched Izod impact test [2]. It was observed that reinforcement biomaterials reduced the impact strength of F1, F2 and F3 biocomposites compared to that of the matrix by 65% 85% and 83% respectively. These biocomposites had also lower impact strength then RTV 132 UV Talc/PP commercial composite.

<i>Sample Number</i>	<i>PP/POE/MAPP (J/m)</i>	<i>F1 (J/m)</i>	<i>F2 (J/m)</i>	<i>F3 (J/m)</i>
1	586,8	321,07	101,93	151,77
2	660,83	303,88	126,91	132,68
3	926,83	281,07	140,94	134,32
4	933,54	288,47	108,74	138,43
5	1057,67	273,33	146,16	126,91
6	703,78	299,56	146,47	155,94
Mean	856,57	294,56	128,53	140
Standard-Deviation	150,31	17,23	19,43	11,42

Table 3: Impact strength of the biocomposites and the matrix material.

Figure 7: Impact strength of A: PP/POE/MAPP; B: RTP 132 UV Talc/PP; C: F1; D: F2; E: F3

5 CONCLUSIONS

At ambient temperature (25°C), experimental results showed that both of the reinforcement materials improved tensile modulus as well as flexural modulus and strength of the matrix. The miscanthus fibres were more effective than the biocarbon particles. However, a reversed effect was observed for the case of the tensile strength of the F1 biocomposite with biocarbon particles as reinforcement material.

The SEM images of the tensile and flexural fractured surfaces showed crack around the biocarbon particle and clean surface of pulled-out fibres suggesting the weak adhesion between the reinforcement material and the matrix that might cause the reduction of the composites tensile strength.

It was also found that the temperature reduced the tensile properties of biomaterials reinforced PP/POE.

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